

Research Paper

Soil improvement with laponite: effects on soil-structure interaction in liquefiable sands

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the effects of laponite treatment as a mitigation technique against seismically induced soil liquefaction and its influence on soil-structure interaction. Firstly, undrained cyclic triaxial tests are conducted on clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands. The tests confirm that laponite could enhance the resistance of the treated sand against liquefaction and that the constitutive model PM4Sand is able to capture the main aspects of the dynamic behavior of both clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands, by adjusting the relevant constitutive parameters. Then, two-dimensional plane-strain finite element models are constructed using OpenSees and PM4Sand based on the centrifuge tests involving two schemes of laponite treatment. The numerical results match well with the centrifuge test data, thus verifying the validity of the numerical soil-structure systems. Finally, the numerical models are re-configured to test the effects of laponite treatment on the soil-structure interaction of a shallow buried tunnel, a surface structure, and a combination of the two in liquefiable soils.

1. Introduction

Liquefaction is a process during which the shear stiffness and strength of saturated loose soil are temporarily lost. It is characterized by an increase in pore pressure and could lead to the complete loss of effective stress. Both surface and underground structures could suffer severe damages in liquefied soils. Particularly, earthquake-induced liquefaction poses a major threat to all engineering structures (Bray et al., 2017; Hazarika et al., 2017; Ozkula et al., 2023; Bao et al., 2024; Flora et al., 2024; Guo et al., 2025; Qin et al., 2025).

To mitigate the risk of liquefaction, various countermeasures have been developed (Flora et al., 2023). Besides ground reinforcement with inclusions, i.e., jet grouting or deep mixing columns, and mitigation by induced partial saturation (Flora et al., 2021), typical interventions include in-situ densification, enhanced drainage, and soil stabilization through grouting (Bhanwar and Dave, 2021). In-situ densification such as vibro- (Shenthan et al., 2004), dynamic (Feng et al., 2015), and explosive compactions (Gohl et al., 2000) can increase the relative density of the soil, thus improving its resistance against liquefaction. However, they are scarcely applicable in densely populated areas,

because the existing structures will be strongly disturbed by the compacting processes. Drainage enhancement (Brennan and Madabhushi, 2002; Rollins et al., 2004) can improve the permeability of the soil to drain out any possible excess pore pressure (EPP). Nevertheless, this method faces challenges such as high construction difficulty and cost, and its effectiveness is not always guaranteed (Rasouli et al., 2016). Therefore, it is often employed in conjunction with other techniques to ensure comprehensive mitigation (Bahadori et al., 2018). The third method, i.e., grouting, could significantly increase the shear strength of the soil by filling up the voids among the particles (Martin and Olgun, 2006). Its effects are closely related to the features of the grout, and there are some exciting developments in this front brought by the introduction of novel nanomaterials.

For example, colloidal silica (Gallagher and Mitchell, 2000) and bentonite (Gratchev et al., 2007) have been proven effective in preventing liquefaction, and, more recently, the invention of laponite (Shumsun et al., 2023) offered yet another promising candidate for the same purpose. These three nanomaterials are all environmental-friendly and nontoxic, which is a prominent feature that distinguishes them from conventional grouts such as cement, chemical solutions, and epoxy

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(Shumsun et al., 2023). In addition, the three nanomaterials can form suspensions with low initial viscosity when mixed with water (Huang and Wang, 2016; Bao et al., 2019). Hence, the grouting could be carried out without high grout pressure, leaving nearby structures much less disturbed (Gallagher and Finsterle, 2004; Hwang et al., 2011; Huang et al., 2019). After a certain aging period, which normally takes 48 to 168 h, these suspensions would change into a gel formation with high viscosity (El Mohtar et al., 2013; Bao et al., 2019). Then, the gel formation of any one of the nanomaterials could have a bridging effect (Huang and Wang, 2016; Krishnan and Shukla, 2021) among the soil grains effectively constraining their movement, thereby providing the soil with additional shearing strength and stiffness (Ochoa-Cornejo et al., 2016).

Laponite, in particular, with the general formula of $\text{Na}^{+0.7}[(\text{Si}_8\text{Mg}_{5.5}\text{Li}_{0.3})\text{O}_{20}(\text{OH})_4]^{-0.7}$, is a synthetic layered nano-clay similar to natural hectorite with a thickness of 1 nm and a diameter of 25 nm (El Howayek, 2011). It is formed by a magnesium octahedral sheet sandwiched between two silica tetrahedral sheets. In dry state, it manifests as white powder. After mixing with water, it can form the suspension with an initial viscosity close to that of clear water. However, the viscosity of the suspension will increase over time and even become hundreds of times larger (Huang and Wang, 2016). Due to the foregoing properties, laponite has been used as a rheological modifier in multiple fields. Compared with colloidal silica of 100 nm and bentonite of 1000 nm, laponite has a smaller particle size of 25 nm, allowing a more penetrative and uniform distribution of the fines into the pores of the soil (Ochoa-Cornejo et al., 2016; Krishnan and Shukla, 2021). Meanwhile, the plasticity index of laponite is circa 1200 % (Tobar and Orense, 2021), almost 3.5 times that of bentonite, which is 350 % (Noori et al., 2019), so laponite can be much more effective as a soil additive than the same amount of bentonite.

The effects of laponite in liquefaction mitigation have been confirmed by numerous specimen tests. The accumulation of EPP is greatly delayed and reduced in laponite-treated specimens subject to cyclic shearing compared with untreated counterparts (Huang and Wang, 2016; Mele et al., 2018). The level of improvement is found to be positively related to the percentage of laponite and the aging time before shearing (Ochoa-Cornejo et al., 2016).

On a larger scale with more complicated boundary conditions, centrifuge tests were conducted to obtain more insights into the working mechanisms of laponite. Wang et al. (2018) and Huang et al. (2019) performed centrifuge shaking tests on a reservoir embankment and a soil foundation, respectively, and the laponite-treated soils showed marked reductions in EPP, soil settlement, lateral displacement, and shear strain. Miranda et al. (2023) did a series of centrifuge shaking tests on a shallow tunnel with an adjacent surface structure in liquefiable ground. The laponite treatment significantly reduced the uneven uplift of the tunnel and the uneven settlement of the surface structure, which indicated that the structure-soil-structure interaction (SSSI) has been weakened.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, a comprehensive constitutive relation that incorporates the rheological characteristics of laponite suspension as pore fluid has not been developed yet. Nevertheless, it is possible to capture the main aspects of the dynamic behavior of laponite-treated soil using currently available ones. Tobar and Orense (2021) conducted numerical simulations of a single-story structure resting on liquefiable soil deposit adopting the GEFDyn code (Aubry et al., 1986). The Hujeux constitutive model (Hujeux, 1985) was used for both clean and laponite-treated sands. For the latter, the elastic moduli and the internal friction angle were specially configured. As validated by drained and undrained simple shear tests, the Hujeux constitutive model with adjusted parameters can yield the responses of laponite-treated soil with reasonable accuracy.

This paper aims to investigate, at a macro-scale level, the effect of laponite treatment as a mitigation technique against seismically induced soil liquefaction and its influence on soil-structure interaction (SSI). Firstly, undrained cyclic triaxial tests are conducted to validate the

applicability of the PM4Sand constitutive model (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou, 2017) for both clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands, with appropriate macroscopic adjustments to the constitutive parameters. Then, more sophisticated plane-strain finite element models are constructed using OpenSees (PEER, 2021) based on the centrifuge tests by Miranda et al. (2023). Finally, the numerical models are re-configured for further discussions on the issue.

2. The constitutive relations

2.1. The PM4Sand constitutive model

Laponite suspension, as the pore fluid, greatly complicates the dynamic stress-strain relationship of saturated soil. However, it is possible to account for the main aspects of its behavior using presently available constitutive models by adjusting the relevant parameters, as achieved by Tobar and Orense (2021) and, similarly with bentonite, by Santagata and Bobet (2012). In this section, the constitutive model PM4Sand is examined to check whether it is capable of modelling the responses of clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands subject to cyclic shearing under undrained conditions.

PM4Sand is a constitutive model specifically developed for the purpose of geotechnical earthquake engineering (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou, 2017). The model is based on the principles of critical state soil mechanics, and it can simulate the nonlinear behavior of sand under cyclic shear loading (Zhang et al., 2023b; Zhang et al., 2024a). There are totally 27 parameters in the constitution of PM4Sand, and 8 of them are to be calibrated in this study through cyclic triaxial (TRX) tests, as listed in Table 1, while the rest 19 ones adopt the default correlations established by Boulanger and Ziotopoulou (2017). For laponite-treated sand, some of the parameters need to be further adjusted. To identify them, the physical meanings of the parameters and the working mechanisms of laponite are discussed.

The philosophy to which the authors subscribe is that the laponite should be considered part of the gel formation occupying the void space; ergo, the laponite does not belong to the particles constituting the skeleton of the soil. Therefore, the maximum and minimum void ratios e_{\max} and e_{\min} and the relative density D_r are unaffected by it. In PM4Sand, the critical state line is defined by Bolton's (1986) dilatancy relationship

$$D_{r,cs} = \frac{R}{Q - \ln(100 \frac{p'}{p_A})} \quad (1)$$

where $D_{r,cs}$ is the critical state relative density; p' is the mean effective

Table 1
Constitutive parameters of clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands for PM4Sand.

Parameter	Hostun sands in the TRX tests		Hostun sands in Models 3/4 of the centrifuge tests	
	Clean	Laponite-treated	Clean	Laponite-treated
e_{\max} , maximum void ratio	1.049			
e_{\min} , minimum void ratio	0.648			
D_r , relative density	50 %/60 %		57 %/62 %	
Q , critical state line parameter	8.4			
R , critical state line parameter	0.78			
ρ , mass density: Mg/m ³	1.89/1.91	1.91/1.93	1.96/1.98	1.97/2.00
G_0 , shear modulus constant	250	350	750	1050
h_{p0} , contraction rate parameter	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.07

stress; p_A is the atmospheric pressure of 101 kPa; Q and R are Bolton's constants. Thus, by the same rationale, the critical state parameters Q and R are the intrinsic properties of the soil irrelevant to whatever the pore fluid is. Hence, Q and R remain unchanged, too. That concludes the parameters that are presumed to be consistent for clean and laponite-treated sands.

Because laponite has a specific gravity larger than that of water, laponite suspension as pore fluid would increase the density of fully saturated soil. It is calculated by

$$\rho = \frac{\rho_w G_s + \rho_f e}{1 + e}, \quad (2)$$

where ρ_w and ρ_f are the densities of water and the pore fluid, respectively; G_s is the specific gravity of the soil particles; e is the void ratio. Since laponite is insoluble in water, the density of laponite suspension is

$$\rho_f = \frac{\rho_w G_L (1 + \omega_L)}{G_L + \omega_L}, \quad (3)$$

where G_L is the specific gravity of the laponite particles, which is 2.57; ω_L is the concentration rate expressed in mass percent.

The laponite suspension, after some aging time, would change into a gel formation that contributes to the overall shearing stiffness of the soil, especially when the shear strain is small, and the gel formation is in a solid-like state with high viscosity (Tobar and Orense, 2021). Therefore, the shear modulus coefficient G_0 should be enhanced for laponite-treated sand. As reported by Ochoa-Cornejo (2017) and Tobar and Orense (2021), an increment of 20 % to 50 % is seen on the small-strain shear modulus of sand treated by a laponite suspension of 5 % concentration rate.

The principal anti-liquefaction effect of laponite suspension stems from its constraint on the soil particles, which reduces to a minimum the mutual mobility of sand grains, thus offering additional resistance against volumetric strain accumulation, either contraction or dilation (Tobar and Orense, 2022). In PM4Sand, this aspect of the soil behavior is controlled by the contraction rate parameter h_{p0} , which governs the dilatancy of the sand (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou, 2017). The larger h_{p0} is, the lesser and slower the contraction becomes. Hence, it is possible to model the effects of laponite on loose sand by adopting a larger value of h_{p0} . Conventionally, h_{p0} is calibrated to match the experimental Cyclic Resistance Ratio (CRR) vs Cycles to Reach Liquefaction (N_{liq}) data (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou, 2017; Zhang et al., 2023b; Zhang et al., 2024a). In Huang and Wang (2016) and Ochoa-Cornejo et al. (2016), a 3.5 % laponite suspension with 2-day aging and a 1 % laponite suspension with 3-day aging were tried on Shanghai and Ottawa sands, respectively, and the amplitudes of the deviatoric stress required for the sands to reach liquefaction within the same number of loading cycles were nearly doubled. Hence, for the numerical modelling of laponite-treated sand using PM4Sand, the h_{p0} parameter should be recalibrated to match the higher CRR values.

2.2. Experimental verification

To verify the applicability of PM4Sand and the aforementioned parametric adjustments, a series of undrained TRX tests are conducted on clean and laponite-treated Hostun sand at the Soil Mechanics Laboratory of the Department of Civil, Architectural and Environmental Engineering in the University of Naples Federico II (Italy), using the stress-path controlled Bishop-Wesley triaxial apparatus as shown in Fig. 1 (Aversa and Vinale, 1995).

Hostun sand is a typical sand of France and has been frequently used in liquefaction-related studies (Kassas et al., 2021; Lewis and Adamidis, 2024). It is characterized by a high degree of particle uniformity as shown in Fig. 2 (Flavigny et al., 1990) and a specific weight G_s of 2.65. It is also a standardized geomaterial, which allows for consistent behavior in geotechnical tests, thus enabling the control of experimental variables

Fig. 1. Undrained cyclic triaxial tests on Hostun sand at University of Naples Federico II.

Fig. 2. Grain size distribution of Hostun sand (Flavigny et al., 1990).

and comparative analyses.

The clean and laponite-treated specimens are prepared at the nominal initial relative densities of 50 % and 60 %, adopting the maximum and minimum void ratios of 1.049 and 0.648 (Kassas et al., 2021). For the laponite-treated ones, to achieve a uniform distribution of laponite within the specimens, the laponite particles are mixed with the sand in dry state. The amount of added laponite is 5 % concentration rate of the suspension, which is equivalent to 1.6 % of the dry weight of sand for specimens with a D_r of 50 % and 1.52 % for specimens with a D_r of 60 %. The sand-laponite mixture is subsequently wet pluviated in a steel cylinder and is then frozen. It is important to note that, prior to freezing, the specimens require an additional 7 days for curing. This period ensures that the gel is fully formed. The frozen specimens are then mounted onto the triaxial cell and are thawed under drained conditions under the effective confining pressure of 10 kPa. After thawing, the specimens are subjected to isotropic consolidation under the effective confining pressures of 50 kPa or 100 kPa as shown in Table 2. Then, different cyclic stress ratios (CSR), defined by $q_{cyc}/(2\sigma'_c)$ and listed as CRR in Table 2, are applied, where q_{cyc} and σ'_c are the deviatoric stress and the effective confining pressure, respectively. In this study, liquefaction triggering is defined according to the stress approach, meaning that the excess pore pressure ratio (EPPR), defined as the ratio between the excess pore water pressure and the effective confining stress, reaches 0.90.

Through the TRX tests, four sets of CRR- N_{liq} data are obtained. They are fitted with a power law to obtain the liquefaction resistance curves in

Table 2
Undrained cyclic triaxial tests on clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands.

No.	D_r (%)	σ'_c (kPa)	Specimen	CRR	N_{liq}
1	50	50	Clean sand	0.14	22
2				0.15	8.0
3				0.16	3.1
4				0.20	1.2
5	50	50	Treated by 5% laponite suspension with 7-day aging	0.14	39
6				0.16	13
7				0.18	5
8				0.20	2
9	60	100	Clean sand	0.12	83
10				0.14	22
11				0.17	4
12	60	100	Treated by 5% laponite suspension with 7-day aging	0.15	90
13				0.16	10
14				0.18	6.1

Fig. 3. Due to the enhanced liquefaction resistance, the laponite-treated specimens must undergo greater CSR for them to reach liquefaction within similar numbers of cycles as the untreated ones do.

Four data points of the clean and laponite-treated specimens under similar deviatoric stresses but different confining pressures, as enclosed in the blue boxes in Fig. 3, have been selected, and the corresponding stress paths are illustrated in Figs. 4 and 5. Clearly, the accumulations of both EPP and axial strains are inhibited by the laponite treatment. These improvements highlight the effectiveness of laponite in enhancing the performance of Hostun sand under cyclic conditions.

For the verification of the PM4Sand constitutive model, some numerical simulations of the TRX tests are performed using OpenSees in 2D axisymmetric conditions (PEER, 2021). The simulations are conducted under applied load conditions. To ensure the reliability of the numerical results, the actual stress time-history data recorded during the TRX tests are used as the input stresses. The re-calibration leads to a set of constitutive parameters for Hostun sand slightly different from those

Fig. 3. Experimental and numerical CRR- N_{liq} data of clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands: (a) $\sigma'_c = 50$ kPa, $D_r = 50$ % and (b) $\sigma'_c = 100$ kPa, $D_r = 60$ %.

Fig. 4. TRX test results of clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands: $\sigma'_c = 50$ kPa, $D_r = 50$ %, CSR = 0.16.

Fig. 5. TRX test results of clean and laponite-treated Hostun sands: $\sigma'_c = 100$ kPa, $D_r = 60\%$, CSR = 0.14 or 0.15.

reported by Kassas et al. (2021). As listed in Table 1, the maximum and minimum void ratios remain consistent as 1.049 and 0.648, respectively (Kassas et al., 2021). The initial relative densities are the same as those in the TRX tests. The Bolton's constants Q and R are 8.4 and 0.78, respectively (Kassas et al., 2021). The specific gravity of the Hostun sand particles is 2.65, and the mass density of 5% laponite suspension is 1.03 Mg/m³. Using Eqs. (2) and (3), the mass densities of the clean and the laponite-treated Hostun sands are 1.89 Mg/m³ and 1.91 Mg/m³ when $D_r = 50\%$ and 1.91 Mg/m³ and 1.93 Mg/m³ when $D_r = 60\%$. G_0 is calibrated by comparing the experimental and numerical stress–strain loops in Fig. 6, and it is 250 and 350 for the clean and laponite-treated sands, respectively. For the calibration of h_{p0} , the CRR- N_{liq} data are matched between the numerical simulation results and the experimental data from the TRX tests as plotted in Fig. 3, with h_{p0} being 0.02 for clean and 0.05 for laponite-treated Hostun sands.

Besides the apparent enhancement of liquefaction resistance by the laponite treatment, for instance, the impeded EPP accumulation in Fig. 6, the parametric adjustments of PM4Sand are capable of modelling the altered stress–strain responses of the specimens during the shearing process. As demonstrated in Fig. 6, the specimen of clean Hostun sand subjected to the CSR of 0.16 in the TRX test reaches the double-amplitude shear strain of 4.1% after merely 3 cycles. In contrast, the laponite-treated specimen under the same CSR must go through 4.3 times the number of cycles to achieve a similar level of axial strain, indicating that the shear strength and stiffness of the sand have been significantly increased. The same enhancement can be quantitatively simulated by the numerical models through macroscopic adjustments to the constitutive parameters. Thus, the TRX tests provide adequate experimental verification for the applicability of PM4Sand in modelling clean and laponite-treated sands. It is noteworthy that some curves in Fig. 6 exhibit jagged fluctuations. This is because the original deviatoric stress time-histories from the TRX tests are not perfectly smooth. However, such fluctuations are relatively minor compared with the general trend of the deviatoric stresses. Hence, they are not visibly apparent in the EPPR lines.

3. Numerical modelling of the centrifuge tests

3.1. The centrifuge tests

In this section, PM4Sand is used for the modelling of more complicated soil–structure systems. The centrifuge tests in Miranda et al. (2023) are selected as the benchmark. Although there were four physical models involved in the tests, only two of them, i.e., Models 3 and 4, included laponite-treated Hostun sand and therefore are the targets of the numerical modelling in the current paper. For the simulations of the two centrifuge tests in clean Hostun sand, i.e., Models 1 and 2 in Miranda et al. (2023), one may refer to Zhang et al. (2023). A comprehensive description of the tests can be found in Miranda et al. (2023). The following is a brief prototype-scale introduction of the two models, where two different schemes of laponite treatment were tried.

The tests were conducted under a centrifugal acceleration of 60g in plane-strain condition. To permit the measurement of displacement by high-speed photogrammetry, a rigid container with transparent frontal view was used. Hence, two absorbent layers of Duxseal material were attached to the lateral walls to mitigate the boundary effects (Steedman and Madabhushi, 1991). The layouts of the two models are illustrated in Fig. 7, both of which consisted of a shallow buried rectangular tunnel and an adjacent single-story surface structure situated in liquefiable Hostun sand. The tunnel and the surface structure were made of aluminum sheets, featuring a Young's modulus of 7×10^7 kPa. Their weights were 410.4 Mg and 209.5 Mg, respectively. Given the out-of-plane length of 15 m and the in-plane dimensions, the tunnel had an apparent density of 0.68 Mg/m³, and the bearing pressure at the foundations of the surface structure was 57.0 kPa. The initial relative densities of the Hostun sand were 44% and 47% in Models 3 and 4, corresponding to the void ratios of 0.82 and 0.80, respectively (Miranda et al., 2023). They are calculated based on the maximum and minimum void ratios reported by Flavigny et al. (1990), differing from those used in the numerical simulations in the subsequent sections, which are based on the parameters provided by Kassas et al. (2021).

The most prominent distinction between the two models was the treatment by a laponite suspension of 5% concentration rate. In Model 3, the laponite-permeated sand formed an entire block underneath the

Fig. 6. Comparison of stress-path data between the experimental and the numerical TRX tests for (a) Clean Hostun sand, CSR = 0.16, $D_r = 50\%$, $\sigma'_c = 50$ kPa, (b) Laponite-treated Hostun sand, CSR = 0.16, $D_r = 50\%$, $\sigma'_c = 50$ kPa.

tunnel. In Model 4, the laponite was used on two vertical stripes at either side of the tunnel. In both models, the aging time for the laponite suspension was 7 days prior to the tests.

After the models had stabilized under the centrifugal acceleration, they were subjected to a series of horizontal shakings. Massive liquefaction of the Hostun sand occurred when the input excitations in Fig. 8 were fired. The signals had similar waveforms and amplitudes, primarily comprising 10 near-harmonic cycles of 1 Hz frequency and 0.40g acceleration. During the tests, the acceleration, pore pressure, and displacement data were recorded by accelerometers (ACC), pore pressure transducers (PPT), and particle image velocimetry (PIV), respectively. Their positions are marked in Fig. 7.

3.2. The numerical modelling

As shown in Fig. 9, two plane-strain numerical models are constructed in prototype scale using the finite element program OpenSees (PEER, 2021). The Hostun sand and the Duxseal layers are modelled by displacement–pressure ($u-p$) coupled quadrilateral elements, i.e., the SSPquadUP elements in OpenSees (McGann et al., 2012). The nominal element size is 0.5 m, complying with the limitation set by Mullen and Belytschko (1982).

The Hostun sand has been assigned the constitutive model of PM4Sand. Since the calibration of the constitutive parameters follows the same procedure elaborated in Kassas et al. (2021), the maximum and minimum void ratios of 1.049 and 0.648 are adopted herein. Hence, the initial relative densities of Hostun sand in Models 3 and 4 were calculated as 57% and 62%, respectively, with the initial void ratios

Fig. 7. Prototype-scale illustrations of (a) Model 3 and (b) Model 4 in the centrifuge tests by Miranda et al. (2023). (Unit: m).

Fig. 8. Accelerograms and spectra of the input excitations in the centrifuge tests.

maintained as 0.82 and 0.80. Same to the parametric adjustments in the previous section, the laponite-treated Hostun sand has larger shear modulus constant G_0 and contraction rate parameter h_{p0} compared with the clean sand, as listed in Table 1. To achieve higher accuracy in modelling the centrifuge tests in given boundary conditions, the G_0 parameter is based on the shear wave velocities obtained through air hammer tests prior to the shakings (Miranda et al., 2023). The Duxseal layers have a simpler linear elastic material type, with a Young's modulus of 800 kPa, a mass density of 1.65 Mg/m³, and a Poisson's ratio of 0.46 (Popescu and Prevost, 1993).

Apart from the constitutive parameters, the permeability coefficient is required for the definition of the u - p coupled elements. For the clean Hostun sand, it is 7.84×10^{-3} m/s (Kassas et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023b; Zhang et al., 2024a). For the laponite-treated Hostun sand, the permeability coefficient could be estimated using the following equation

(Mele et al. 2018)

$$\frac{k_L}{k_p} = \frac{\mu_p \gamma_L}{\mu_L \gamma_p}, \quad (4)$$

where k , μ , and γ are the permeability coefficient, viscosity, and specific weight of the pore fluid, respectively. The subscripts L and p denote the laponite suspension and the reference pore fluid, respectively. In the centrifuge tests, an aqueous solution of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, whose viscosity was 60 times that of water, namely 60 mPa · s, was used to saturate the so-called clean Hostun sand, thus complying with the time scaling laws and ensuring compatibility between the diffusion and the dynamic time (Miranda et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the viscosity of the 5% laponite suspension is 45000 mPa · s after the aging time of 7 days (Wang et al., 2018). Since the specific weights of the two pore fluids are almost identical, their permeability coefficients have the following

Fig. 9. Finite-element meshes of (a) Model 3 and (b) Model 4. (Unit: m).

relationship

$$\frac{k_L}{k_p} = 1.4 \times 10^{-3}. \tag{5}$$

Thus, k_L is estimated to be 1.10×10^{-5} m/s. Although the laponite suspension has extraordinary rheological features, its bulk modulus is measured to be very close to that of water, being 2.2×10^6 kPa throughout days of curing.

The tunnel and the surface structure are modelled by elastic beam elements, whose linear mass density ρ , cross-sectional area A , moment of inertia I , and Young's modulus E have been annotated in Fig. 9. The foundations of the surface structure use the same $u-p$ elements as the surrounding soil, but they have a linear elastic material type with a Young's modulus of 7×10^7 kPa and a mass density of 2.65 Mg/m^3 . The tangential soil-tunnel interface adopts an elastic-perfectly-plastic material to model the frictional sliding behavior, with an elastic modulus of 30 MPa, which is about two thirds of the small-strain shear modulus of the clean sand, and a yield strain threshold of 0.02 (Brinkgreve et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2023b).

The entire model is vertically supported at the base, while the upper edge is defined as a free surface of open drainage. To imitate the boundary conditions of the rigid container, the seismic excitations plotted in Fig. 8 are input horizontally from both the base and the two lateral sides. Rayleigh damping is applied, with a mass matrix factor of 0.047 and a stiffness matrix factor of 0.0004, amounting to a damping of 0.5 % at the dominant frequency of 1 Hz.

The computation is carried out in two stages. The first stage is the application of the gravitational field and the achievement of the initial geo-static equilibrium. This stage corresponds to the spin-up of the centrifuge basket. The second stage is the shaking test, where full liquefaction of the soil is anticipated.

3.3. Experimental verification

To verify the validity of the numerical modelling, the centrifuge test data and the numerical simulation results are compared in Fig. 10. Those include the uplift of the tunnel, the settlements of the surface structure, the EPP, and the acceleration responses of the sand. They are generally well matched for both models. Particularly, at the position of ACC2 in Model 4, the numerical simulation even successfully replicates the amplification and the attenuation of the acceleration responses before

and after full liquefaction. The overall validity of the numerical models is thus confirmed by the data comparison, and the validated numerical soil-structure systems are then used for further investigation on the effects of laponite treatment on SSI in liquefiable sands.

4. Effects of laponite treatment on SSI in liquefiable sands

Before the numerical investigation, a few changes of the model are necessary to achieve a better resemblance to realistic engineering problems. Firstly, the Duxseal layers are removed, and periodic boundary conditions are defined on the two lateral sides, where nodes at the same height are constrained to have the same horizontal displacements. Then, a sensitivity analysis is performed to ensure that the width of the ground is sufficient to avoid interferences on the SSI from the lateral boundaries, and it is found that 100 m are wide enough for that, while the height remains 17.1 m. Thirdly, the excitation signal has the same waveform as the accelerogram of Model 4 in Fig. 8, but its amplitude is multiplied by a factor of 0.4, resulting in an amplitude of 0.15 g, and the source of input is solely from the base of the soil. This adjustment helps induce a similar degree of liquefaction as that in the centrifuge tests (Zhang et al., 2023b; Zhang et al., 2024a). It also scales the Arias Intensity (Arias, 1970) of the shaking to 0.87 m/s, which is now at a similar level of typical strong seismic events such as 0.8 m/s in Bao et al. (2024) and 2.7 m/s in Erazo (2024). Finally, a mid-column is added to the rectangular cross section to imitate the features of actual tunnels of such small height-to-width ratios (Yu et al., 2018; Yuan et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2024c). All the following numerical simulations in this paper adhere to the aforementioned configurations.

The effects of laponite treatment hereafter specifically refers to a laponite suspension of 5 % concentration rate and an aging period of 7 days. To provide an intuitive comparison against the simulations with laponite treatment, three reference models of untreated sand are computed. As illustrated in Fig. 11, they are referred to as Reference Models A, B, and C, where a tunnel, a surface structure, and a combination of the two are considered, respectively. The three models are mostly based on Model 4 of the centrifuge tests, i.e., similar structural properties and untreated clean Hostun sand with the initial relative density of 62 %.

Fig. 10. Comparison between the centrifuge test data and the numerical simulation results.

4.1. Effects of laponite treatment on shallow buried tunnel

In Reference Model A, as illustrated in Fig. 11(a), a shallow tunnel is buried in untreated clean Hostun sand, and the dynamic responses are plotted in Fig. 12, including the average uplift of V1 and V2, the V1-minus-V2 uneven uplift, and the EPPR at P1, P2, P3, and P4. The typical racking deformation of rectangular tunnel is considered of lesser importance in the case of fully liquefied soil (Zhang et al., 2023b; Zhang et al., 2024a). Due to the symmetry of the soil-structure system, the uneven uplift of the tunnel is nearly zero. Hence, the dominant pattern of the tunnel response is a uniform uplift with a maximum of 0.078 m and a residual of 0.066 m. The presence of the tunnel also greatly changes the EPPR within the liquefiable sand layer. As plotted in Fig. 12 (b), the EPPR at P1 exhibits the smallest peak value during the strong shaking, while those at P3 and P4 are nearly 1. The EPPR at P2 attains

the largest peak value, even reaching 1.4. The same results are seen in the contour of EPPR at 7 s in Fig. 13(a). For P1, the tunnel blocks the upward migration of the pore fluid. For P2, the tunnel blocks the dissipation of the pore water, leading to significant accumulation of EPP beneath the tunnel. This results in an abnormal EPPR, being larger than unity. To restore equilibrium, stress redistribution occurs in the said area, manifesting through the uplift of the tunnel. This mechanism is the origin of the uplift force due to EPP, which has been described in Koseki et al. (1997). Although EPPR being greater than unity is avoidable by adopting the even-current vertical effective stress instead of the initial vertical effective stress (Tsiapas et al., 2021; Chaloulos et al., 2021), in this particular case, the unusually large EPPR at P2 could help explain the uplift of the tunnel due to soil liquefaction. After the strong shaking has ended, the tunnel starts to settle from 15 s. This downward movement compresses the lower soil, so the EPPR at P2 abnormally increases

Fig. 11. The Reference Models in untreated clean sand.

Fig. 12. Displacement responses of the shallow tunnel and the EPPR around the tunnel in Reference Model A.

Fig. 13. EPPR contours of Reference Model A during (at 7 s) and after (at 25 s) shaking.

after 15 s, while the others have showed clear signs of dissipation in Fig. 12(b). Since the upward migration of pore fluid is still blocked by the tunnel, there exists an area of sustained EPP beneath it even after the strong shaking, as demonstrated in Fig. 13(b).

As illustrated in Fig. 14, six schemes are tried on the tunnel from Reference Model A. Model A1 is fairly conservative, where the tunnel is encased by a laponite-treated sand layer of 2.5 m thick. In Model A2, there is a gap of 1.5 m between the tunnel exterior and the laponite-treated sand, whose thickness is reduced to 2.0 m. Thus, the laponite treatment encloses a broader area around the tunnel. From Model A3 to Model A6, different portions of the laponite treatment are applied, with the aim to identify which part has priority. The six schemes have all been

symmetrically designed to avoid uneven uplift of the tunnel, so only the average uplifts thereof are compared in Fig. 15. For feasibility reasons, most of the schemes have the laponite treatment closely surrounding the tunnel, so it could be achieved by grouting through holes drilled in the lining. As has been mentioned, a focal point of this numerical investigation is to identify which area around the tunnel should be prioritized, when full-on large-scale laponite treatment is either financially or technically unavailable. Hence, the exact geometry of the treated area is considered of secondary importance.

Predictably, the uplift of the tunnel is much smaller in Model A1. Compared with Reference Model A, the reduction is 38%. The scheme of Model A2 uses 9% more laponite compared with Model A1 to treat a

Fig. 14. Schemes of laponite treatment on shallow buried tunnel. (Unit: m).

Fig. 15. Average uplift of the tunnel in Reference Model A and Models A1 to A6.

larger area around the tunnel. Consequently, the uplift of the tunnel is further reduced by 11 %, achieving a total reduction of 49 %. In Models A3, A4, and A5, the treated sand is above, beneath, and at the sides of the tunnel, respectively. While the uplift is mitigated by 27 % and 12 % in the latter two cases, laponite over the tunnel is not working at all. It even has an adverse effect inducing 3 % more uplift in Model A3. The malfunction of the scheme in Model A3 resonates with the comparison between Models A1 and A6, whose uplifts are nearly identical with or without the overlying portion of the laponite treatment.

The triggering condition of liquefaction-induced uplift of buried underground structure is illustrated in Fig. 16(a), and the following equation could be written (Chian and Madabhushi, 2012; Zhang et al., 2024b)

$$F_B - F_T + F_{EPP} > F_{WS} + F_{SP}, \quad (6)$$

where F_B is the buoyancy force; F_T is the weight of the structure; F_{EPP} is

the force arising from the EPP; F_{WS} is the weight of the overlying soil; F_{SP} is the resistance from the shear planes of the soil. For a given tunnel, F_B and F_T are constant, so only F_{EPP} , F_{WS} , and F_{SP} can possibly be altered as a result of the laponite treatment.

According to Eqs. (2) and (3) and the data in Table 1, the extra mass density brought in by the laponite suspension is trivial and practically negligible. Therefore, the laponite treatment should not be expected to contribute to the uplift resistance through F_{WS} . This explains the non-functioning of the laponite treatment in Model A3.

As for F_{EPP} , Fig. 17 shows that the EPPR beneath the tunnel is greatly reduced if a laponite padding-bottom is present. It has been mentioned in Introduction and confirmed by the triaxial tests that laponite suspension offers additional resistance against volumetric contraction under cyclic shearing. In addition, the high viscosity of the laponite suspension reduces the hydraulic conductivity of the sand. Hence, the laponite treatment impedes the local generation of EPP as well as the migration of high-pressure pore fluid from the other parts, resulting in much lesser F_{EPP} .

The last term in Eq. (6), namely, F_{SP} , is directly reinforced by the enhanced shear strength and stiffness of the laponite-treated sand, especially those at the lateral sides of the tunnel as shown in Fig. 14(e). Nevertheless, there are other aspects to which these two vertical stripes could contribute. Koseki et al. (1997) posited that a buried underground structure must overcome the friction on its side walls during uplift, but this frictional resistance is usually assumed to be zero once the surrounding soil has liquefied. As demonstrated by the EPPR contours in Fig. 17, if the lateral soil undergoes the laponite treatment, its liquefaction susceptibility could be alleviated, and there would exist some form of friction. Furthermore, the two stripes of laponite-treated sand could also suppress the squeezing effect, which is illustrated in Fig. 16(b) and could be seen in all the displacement vectors in Fig. 17, preventing the liquefied soil from deforming towards the base of the tunnel (Schmidt and Hashash, 1999; Chou et al., 2011).

4.2. Effects of laponite treatment on surface structure

In Reference Model B, the single-storey surface structure is situated

Fig. 16. Liquefaction-induced uplift of buried underground structure: (a) Triggering condition and (b) Squeezing effect.

Fig. 17. EPPR contours and displacement vectors of Models A1 to A6 during shaking at 7 s.

in untreated clean Hostun sand, as illustrated in Fig. 11(b). Dynamic responses including the average settlement of V3 and V4, the uneven settlement of V3-minus-V4, and the EPPR of P5, P6, and P7 are plotted in Fig. 18. Again, due to the symmetry of the model, the uneven settlement is nearly zero throughout, and the structure mainly exhibits uniform settlement. Compared with the tunnel, the surface structure has limited influence on the EPPR as demonstrated by the contours in Fig. 19(a). However, the maximum EPPR beneath the two foundations, i.e., P5 and P6 in Fig. 18(b), are only 0.22 because of the extra vertical effective stress from the structural weight. This phenomenon has also been observed in many other shaking table tests (Dashti et al., 2010; Bertalot and Brennan, 2015; Lirer et al., 2024).

A similar series of six schemes are tried on the surface structure from Reference Model B as illustrated in Fig. 20. In Model B1, an entire block of the foundation soil is treated with a width of 10 m and a height of 6 m. Then, different portions of the block are in effect in Models A2 to A6, and

the average settlements of the surface structure are plotted in Fig. 21. The laponite treatment in these schemes does not exceed the depth of 6 m, so it should be relatively easy to implement.

The settlements are mainly caused by the shear failure and the contraction of the liquefiable soil (Dashti et al., 2010), both of which can be remedied by laponite. Therefore, in all the six models of Fig. 20, the settlements have been reduced compared with Reference Model B. Counterintuitively, although the scheme in Model B1 has been intended as most conservative, it turns out to be second most effective, reducing the settlement by 55 %. In Model B2, where the same block of foundation soil is encased by a layer of laponite-treated soil of 1.5 m thick, the settlement is decreased by 57 %. Since the amount of laponite used in Model B2 is far less, only 48 % of that in Model B1, it is reasonable to conclude that the scheme in Model B2 would be the most cost-effective solution. As shown in Fig. 22, the effects of the two schemes in reducing EPP accumulation are basically the same. The slightly larger settlement

Fig. 18. Displacement responses of the surface structure and the EPPR around the structure in Reference Model B.

Fig. 19. EPPR contours of Reference Model B during (at 7 s) and after (at 25 s) shaking.

Fig. 20. Schemes of laponite treatment on surface structure. (Unit: m).

Fig. 21. Average settlement of the surface structure in Reference Model B and Models B1 to B6.

in Model B1 is a result of the treated soil settling down as a stiff block, while the same area in Model B2 is more deformable and hence less inclined to behave like a foreign object in the ground.

The effects of the other four schemes are somewhat similar, reducing the settlement of the surface structure by 16 % to 35 %. Although the scheme of Model B3 does not achieve the maximum reduction in settlement of the surface structure, it demonstrates superior material efficiency by employing 42 % less laponite compared to Model B2, while maintaining 67 % of its settlement mitigation effectiveness. Therefore, when large-scale treatment is restricted due to either financial or other reasons, the proper way to fully to exploit the limited amount of available laponite is to apply it directly beneath the foundations of the surface structure, thus creating enhanced supporting columns within the liquefiable soil. Given the shallow-foundation prerequisite of this paper, this kind of treatment should be relatively easy.

4.3. Effects of laponite treatment on shallow buried tunnel and surface structure

In Reference Model C, the tunnel and the surface structure are both included, as illustrated in Fig. 11(c). This particular arrangement in liquefiable soil has been extensively analyzed in another companion paper (Zhang et al., 2023b). As shown in Fig. 23(a) and (b), the tunnel-structure system leads to a more asymmetric distribution of EPPR. Thus, the SSSI mainly manifests through the uneven uplift and settlement in Fig. 24, amounting to 0.050 m and 0.046 m, respectively. This new mechanism is clearly indicated by the comparison of the deformed ground surfaces in Fig. 25. While the soil-structure systems remain nearly symmetric before and after the shaking in Reference Models A and B, there is a general inclination of clockwise rotation in Reference Model C.

For the SSSI case in Reference Model C, three schemes are tried as illustrated in Fig. 26. Because of the asymmetry of the tunnel and the surface structure, this is the only situation where some of the laponite has been deployed asymmetrically. Model C1 is the simple combination of Model A1 in Fig. 14(a) plus Model B2 in Fig. 20(b). In Model C2, the laponite treated sand forms three vertical barriers in an attempt to restrain the SSSI. In Model C3, the tunnel and the surface structure are isolated from the outside by a layer of laponite-treated soil of 2.0 m thick. Again, the focal point of this numerical investigation is to identify which area of the foundation soil should be prioritized, so practices could be guided. The exact geometry of the treated area is considered of secondary importance. The average and uneven vertical displacements of the tunnel and the surface structure are plotted in Fig. 27.

It is expected that the average uplift and settlement are much smaller in Model C1 compared to those in Reference Model C. However, the uneven settlement is barely controlled. It even has an increment of 70 %. As shown in Fig. 28(a), although Model C1 has the least EPP accumulation during the shaking, yet, its distribution, especially around the tunnel and the surface structure, is most asymmetric among the three, hence exacerbating the unbalanced movements.

The three so-called barriers in Model C2 reduce the average uplift

Fig. 22. EPPR contours and displacement vectors of Models B1 to B6 during shaking at 7 s.

Fig. 23. EPPR contours of Reference Model C during (at 7 s) and after (at 25 s) shaking.

Fig. 24. Displacement and rotation responses of the tunnel and the surface structure in Reference Model C.

Fig. 25. Deformed ground surfaces in (a) Reference Model A, (b) Reference Model B, and (c) Reference Model C.

and settlement, but the uneven displacements are worse. The problem is that the central stripe constrains the uplift of the right side of the tunnel and the settlement of the left foundation of the surface structure, which is exactly why the two rotate clockwise in Reference Model C as plotted in Fig. 25(c). In effect, this scheme amplifies the SSSI rather than preventing it.

Overall, the encasing laponite-treated sand layer in Model C3 outperforms the other two in a general sense. The average uplift and settlement are reduced by 33 % and 43 %, respectively. More importantly, the rotation of the tunnel and the surface structure are down by 34 % and 37 %, respectively. As shown in Fig. 28(c), the EPPR within the isolated zone is milder while maintaining a certain extent of uniformity

and symmetry. On the left bound, the laponite-treated soil helps reduce the uplift of the tunnel, while, on the opposite side, it constrains the settlement of the right foundation of the surface structure. Thus, the clockwise rotation in Reference Model C is counterbalanced.

5. Conclusions

This paper investigates the effects of laponite treatment as a mitigation technique against seismically induced soil liquefaction and its effects on SSI. The main conclusions are as follows:

Fig. 26. Schemes of laponite treatment on shallow buried tunnel and surface structure. (Unit: m).

Fig. 27. Vertical displacements of the tunnel and the surface structure in Reference Model C and Models C1 to C3.

Fig. 28. EPPR contours of Models C1 to C3 during shaking.

- (1) A series of undrained cyclic triaxial tests are conducted on clean and laponite-treated Hostun sand. The tests, once again, confirm that laponite could enhance the resistance of the treated sand against liquefaction.
- (2) Although, to the best of the authors' knowledge, a comprehensive constitutive relation that incorporates the rheological characteristics of laponite suspension as pore fluid has not been developed yet, it is possible to capture the main aspects of the dynamic behavior of laponite-treated soil using currently available ones, as has been done in this paper using PM4Sand, by adjusting the relevant constitutive parameters.
- (3) Two-dimensional plane-strain finite element models are constructed based on the centrifuge tests by Miranda et al. (2023) using PM4Sand for clean and laponite-treated Hostun sand. The numerical results match well with the centrifuge test data, thus verifying the validity of the numerical soil-structure systems, which are then re-configured to test the effects of different schemes of laponite treatment. While only a limited number of schemes are tried in certain situations, some important conclusions have been drawn.
- (4) For a shallow buried tunnel, the laponite treatment is best used beneath and at the lateral sides of the tunnel to reduce liquefaction-induced uplift. For a surface structure in liquefiable soil, the most cost-effective way to mitigate settlement is to encase a block of the foundation soil by a layer of laponite-treated soil. The same applies to the situation where the tunnel is adjacent to the surface structure, and both of them could be contained in an isolated zone surrounded by a layer of laponite-treated soil.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jinghua Zhang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Zhihua Yang:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Emilio Bilotta:** Writing – review & editing. **Lucia Mele:** Data curation. **Qing Sun:** Writing – review & editing. **Haitao Yu:** Data curation. **Yong Yuan:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2025.107360>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

Arias, A., 1970. A measure of earthquake intensity. *Seismic Design Nucl. Plants* 438–483.

- Aubry, D., Chouvet, D., Modaressi, A., Modaressi, H., 1986. GEFDYN : Logiciel d'analyse de comportement mécanique des sols par éléments finis avec prise en compte du couplage sol-eau-air. *Manuel Scientifique, Ecole Centrale Paris, LMSS-Mat*.
- Aversa, S., Vinale, F., 1995. Improvements to a stress-path triaxial cell. *Geotech. Test. J.* 18 (1), 116–120. <https://doi.org/10.1520/GTJ10128J>.
- Bahadori, H., Farzalizadeh, R., Barghi, A., Hasheminezhad, A., 2018. A comparative study between gravel and rubber drainage columns for mitigation of liquefaction hazards. *J. Rock Mech. Geotech.* 10 (5), 924–934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2018.03.008>.
- Bao, X., Jin, Z., Cui, H., Chen, X., Xie, X., 2019. Soil liquefaction mitigation in geotechnical engineering: an overview of recently developed methods. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 120, 273–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2019.01.020>.
- Bao, X., Yuan, H., Shen, J., Liu, C., Chen, X., Cui, H., 2024. Numerical analysis of seismic response of a circular tunnel-rectangular underpass system in liquefiable soil. *Comput. Geotech.* 174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2024.106642>.
- Bertalot, D., Brennan, A.J., 2015. Influence of initial stress distribution on liquefaction-induced settlement of shallow foundations. In: *Geotechnical Earthquake Engineering – Geotechnique Symposium in Print 2015*, pp. 89–99. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.SIP.15.P.002>.
- Bhanwar, P., Dave, T., 2021. A review on soil liquefaction mitigation techniques and its preliminary selection: Vol. 136 LNCE. Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH. doi: 10.1007/978-981-33-6444-8_39.
- Bolton, M.D., 1986. The strength and dilatancy of sands. *Géotechnique* 36 (1), 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1986.36.1.65>.
- Boulanger, R.W., Ziotopoulou, K., 2017. PM4Sand (version 3.1): a sand plasticity model for earthquake engineering applications, report UCD/CGM-15/01. Center for Geotechnical Modeling, University of California, Davis, CA, USA.
- Bray, J.D., Markham, C.S., Cubrinovski, M., 2017. Liquefaction assessments at shallow foundation building sites in the Central Business District of Christchurch, New Zealand. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 92, 153–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.09.049>.
- Brennan, A., Madabhushi, S.P.G., 2002. Effectiveness of vertical drains in mitigation of liquefaction. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 22 (9), 1059–1065. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0267-7261\(02\)00131-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0267-7261(02)00131-8).
- Brinkgreve, R., Kumaeswamy, S., Swolfs, W., 2016. PLAXIS2016 user's manual. <https://www.plaxis.com/kbtags/manuals/>.
- Chian, S.C., Madabhushi, S.P.G., 2012. Effect of soil conditions on uplift of underground structures in liquefied soil. *J. Earthq. Tsunami* 6 (4), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1793431112500200>.
- Chaloulos, Y., Tsiapas, Y., Bouckovalas, G., 2021. Seismic analysis of a model Tension Leg supported Wind Turbine under Seabed Liquefaction. *Ocean Eng.* 238, 109706.
- Chou, J.C., Kutter, B.L., Travarasou, T., Chacko, J.M., 2011. Centrifuge modeling of seismically induced uplift for the BART Transbay tube. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron* 137 (8), 754–765. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0000489](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000489).
- Dashti, S., Bray, J.D., Pestana, J.M., Riemer, M., Wilson, D., 2010. Mechanisms of seismically induced settlement of buildings with shallow foundations on liquefiable soil. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron.* 136 (1), 151–164. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0000179](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000179).
- El Howayek, A., 2011. Characterization, Rheology and Microstructure of Laponite Suspensions. Purdue University.
- El Mohtar, C.S., Bobet, A., Santagata, M.C., Drnevich, V.P., Johnston, C.T., 2013. Liquefaction mitigation using bentonite suspensions. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron.* 139 (8), 1369–1380. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0000865](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0000865).
- Erazo, K., 2024. Analysis and damage correlation of ground motion intensity measures from records of the 2023 Turkey-Syria earthquake. *Bull. Earthq. Eng.* 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-024-01989-8>.
- Feng, S.J., Du, F.L., Shi, Z.M., Shui, W.H., Tan, K., 2015. Field study on the reinforcement of collapsible loess using dynamic compaction. *Eng. Geol.* 185, 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2014.12.006>.
- Flavigny, E., Desrues, J., Palayer, B., 1990. Note technique: le sable d'Hostun RF. *Revue française de géotechnique* 53, 67–70.
- Flora, A., Bilotta, E., Chiaradonna, A., Lirer, S., Mele, L., Pingue, L., 2021. A field trial to test the efficiency of induced partial saturation and horizontal drains to mitigate the susceptibility of soils to liquefaction. *B Earthq. Eng.* 19 (10), 3835–3864. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-020-00914-z>.
- Flora, A., Bilotta, E., Valtucci, F., Fierro, T., Perez, R., Santucci de Magistris, F., Modoni, G., Spacagna, R., Kelesoglu, M.K., Sargin, S., Altinok, E., Oztoprak, S., Bozbeyl, I., Aysal, N., 2024. Liquefaction effects in the city of Gölbaşı: from the analysis of predisposing factors to damage survey. *Eng. Geol.* 338, art. no. 107633. doi: 10.1016/j.enggeo.2024.107633.
- Flora, A., Bilotta, E., Mele, L., Lirer, S., Modoni, G., 2023. Liquefaction mechanisms and mitigation techniques. *Ital Geotech. J.* 57 (2), 33–88. <https://doi.org/10.19199/2023.2.0557-1405.033>.
- Gallagher, P.M., Finsterle, S., 2004. Physical and numerical model of colloidal silica injection for passive site stabilization. *Vadose Zone J.* 3 (3). <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2004.0917>.
- Gallagher, P.M., Mitchell, J.K., 2000. Passive site remediation for mitigation of liquefaction risk. In: *Proceedings of MEDAT-2 Work MCEER, University of Buffalo, SUNY*, pp 149–155.
- Gohl, W.B., Jefferies, M.G., Howie, J.A., Diggles, D., 2000. Explosive compaction: design, implementation and effectiveness. *Geotechnique* 50 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.2000.50.6.657>, 657–665–665.
- Gratchev, I.B., Sassa, K., Osipov, V.I., Fukuoka, H., Wang, G., 2007. Undrained cyclic behavior of bentonite-sand mixtures and factors affecting it. *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* 25 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10706-006-9115-2>.

- Guo, X., Geng, P., Zeng, G., Chang, X., Cai, Q., 2025. Strength evaluation method for circumferential joint of shield tunnel under seismic loading. *Tunn. Undergr. Space Technol.* 159, 106432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2025.106432>.
- Hazarika, H., Kokusho, T., Kayen, R.E., Dashti, S., Fukuda, M., 2017. *Geotechnical damage due to the 2016 Kumamoto Earthquake and future challenges*. *Lowland Technol. Int.* 19 (3), 189–204.
- Huang, Y., Wang, L., 2016. Laboratory investigation of liquefaction mitigation in silty sand using nanoparticles. *Eng. Geol.* 204, 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2016.01.015>.
- Huang, Y., Wen, Z., Wang, L., Zhu, C., 2019. Centrifuge testing of liquefaction mitigation effectiveness on sand foundations treated with nanoparticles. *Eng. Geol.* 249, 249–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enggeo.2019.01.005>.
- Hujeux, J.C., 1985. A constitutive law for the cyclic loading of the soils. *Génie Parasismique*, edited by V. Davidovici and Al. Presses ENPC, 287–302.
- Hwang, H., Rugg, D.A., El Mohtar, C.S., Yoon, J., 2011. Undrained shearing properties of sand permeated with a bentonite suspension for static liquefaction mitigation. *Geo-Frontiers 2011*, 677–686. [https://doi.org/10.1061/41165\(397\)70](https://doi.org/10.1061/41165(397)70).
- Kassas, K., Adamidis, O., Gerolymos, N., Anastasopoulos, I., 2021. Numerical modelling of a structure with shallow strip foundation during earthquake-induced liquefaction. *Géotechnique* 71 (12), 1099–1113. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.19.P.277>.
- Koseki, J., Matsuo, O., Koga, Y., 1997. Uplift behavior of underground structures caused by liquefaction of surrounding soil during earthquake. *Soils Found.* 37 (1), 97. <https://doi.org/10.3208/sandf.37.97>.
- Krishnan, J., Shukla, S., 2021. The utilisation of colloidal silica grout in soil stabilisation and liquefaction mitigation: a state of the art review. *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* 39 (4), 2681–2706. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10706-020-01651-5>.
- Lewis, J., Adamidis, O., 2024. Liquefaction resistance of medium-dense Hostun sand under volumetric contraction. *Japanese Geotech. Soc. Spec. Publ.* 10 (23), 866–871. <https://doi.org/10.3208/jgssp.v10.OS-12-05>.
- Lirer, S., Valtucci, F., Bonassisa, P., Mele, L., Flora, A., 2024. On the liquefaction induced pore water pressure ratio underneath buildings. In: *Geotechnical Engineering Challenges to Meet Current and Emerging Needs of Society*, pp. 1199–1204. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003431749-215>.
- Martin, I.J.R., Olgun, C.G., 2006. Liquefaction mitigation using jet-grout columns—1999 Kocaeli Earthquake Case History. *Ground Modification and Seismic Mitigation* 349–358. [https://doi.org/10.1061/40864\(196\)47](https://doi.org/10.1061/40864(196)47).
- McGann, C.R., Arduino, P., Mackenzie-Helnwein, P., 2012. Stabilized single-point 4-node quadrilateral element for dynamic analysis of fluid saturated porous media. *Acta Geotech.* 7 (4), 297–311. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11440-012-0168-5>.
- Mele, L., Flora, A., Lirer, S., D'Onofrio, A., Bilotta, E., 2018. Experimental study of the injectability and effectiveness of laponite mixtures as liquefaction mitigation technique. In: *Geotechnical Earthquake Engineering and Soil Dynamics V*, pp. 267–275. <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784481486.028>.
- Miranda, G., Nappa, V., Bilotta, E., Madabhushi, G.S.P., 2023. Physical modelling of the interaction between a tunnel and a building in a liquefying ground and its mitigation. *Tunn. Undergr. Space Technol.* 137, 105108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2023.105108>.
- Mullen, R., Belytschko, T., 1982. Dispersion analysis of finite element semidiscretizations of the two-dimensional wave equation. *Int. J. Numer. Methods Engng* 18 (1), 11–29. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.1620180103>.
- Noori, A., Ziaie Moayed, R., Hassanlouard, M., 2019. Dynamic undrained shear strength behavior of bentonite-grouted sand. *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* 37 (5), 4551–4563. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10706-019-00930-0>.
- Ochoa-Cornejo, F., 2017. *Dynamic behavior of sand with nanoparticles*. *ICSMGE 2017–19th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 1071–1074–1074.
- Ochoa-Cornejo, F., Bobet, A., Johnston, C.T., Santagata, M., Sinfield, J.V., 2016. Cyclic behavior and pore pressure generation in sands with laponite, a super-plastic nanoparticle. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 88, 265–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.06.008>.
- Ozkula, G., Dowell, R.K., Baser, T., Lin, J.-L., Numanoglu, O.A., Ilhan, O., Olgun, C.G., Huang, C.-W., Uludag, T.D., 2023. Field reconnaissance and observations from the February 6, 2023, Turkey earthquake sequence. *Nat. Hazards* 119 (1), 663–700. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06143-2>.
- PEER (Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center), 2021. *OpenSees 3.3.0*. Berkeley, CA, USA: Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center, University of California. See <https://opensees.berkeley.edu/> (accessed 20/08/2021).
- Popescu, R., Prevost, J.H., 1993. Centrifuge validation of a numerical model for dynamic soil liquefaction. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 12 (2), 73–90.
- Qin, Y., Zhang, Y., Liu, Z., Liu, X., 2025. Experimental and analytical investigation of the mechanical behavior of deformed segmental tunnel linings strengthened by stainless steel corrugated plate. *Tunn. Undergr. Sp. Tech.* 157, 106355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2024.106355>.
- Rasouli, R., Towhata, I., Akima, T., 2016. Experimental evaluation of drainage pipes as a mitigation against liquefaction-induced settlement of structures. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron.* 142 (9). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001509](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001509).
- Rollins, Kyle M., Goughnour, R. Robert., Anderson, J. K. S., Wade, Stacey F., *Liquefaction hazard mitigation by prefabricated vertical drains*, 2004. International Conference on Case Histories in Geotechnical Engineering. 4. <https://scholarsmine.mst.edu/icchge/5icchge/session12/4>.
- Santagata, M. C., Bobet, A., Witthoef, A.F., 2012. Numerical study of the effectiveness of bentonite treatment for liquefaction mitigation. *GeoCongress 2012*.
- Schmidt, B., Hashash, Y.M.A., 1999. *Preventing Tunnel Flotation Due to Liquefaction*. A. A. Balkema.
- Shenthan, T., Nashed, R., Thevanayagam, S., Martin, G.R., 2004. Liquefaction mitigation in silty soils using composite stone columns and dynamic compaction. *Earthq. Eng. Vib.* 3 (1), 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02668849>.
- Shumsun, N., Jian, D., Eltayeb, M., 2023. Improving the strength properties of sand using laponite, a promising nanoparticle. *Int. J. Civ. Eng.* 21, 679–693. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40999-022-00791-4>.
- Steedman, R., Madabhushi, G., 1991. *Wave propagation in sand medium*. *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Seismic Zonation*. Earthquake Engineering Research Institute.
- Tsiapas, Y., Chaloulos, Y., Bouckovalas, G., Bazaios, K., 2021. *Performance Based Design of Tension Leg Platforms under Seismic Loading and Seabed Liquefaction: A Feasibility Study*. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.*
- Tobar, G.S., Orense, R.P., 2021. Numerical simulation of the effect of laponite on saturated sandy ground in re-liquefaction events. *Aust. Geomech. J.* 56 (4), 109–116–116.
- Tobar, G.S., Orense, R.P., 2022. Geotechnical properties of laponite-treated sands in re-liquefaction events. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron.* 148 (11), 06022011. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0002901](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002901).
- Wang, L., Huang, Y., Wen, Z.Q., 2018. Centrifuge modeling of a constructed reservoir embankment: anti-liquefaction performance improvement using nanoparticles. *J. Perform. Constr. Fac.* 32 (6). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CF.1943-5509.0001225](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CF.1943-5509.0001225).
- Yu, H., Yuan, Y., Xu, G., Su, Q., Yan, X., Li, C., 2018. Multi-point shaking table test for long tunnels subjected to non-uniform seismic loadings – part II: application to the HZM immersed tunnel. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 108, 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.08.018>.
- Yuan, Y., Yu, H., Li, C., Yan, X., Yuan, J., 2018. Multi-point shaking table test for long tunnels subjected to non-uniform seismic loadings – part I: theory and validation. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 108, 177–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.08.017>.
- Zhang, B., Lu, L., Zhong, Z., Du, X., El Naggar, M.H., 2023. Analytical solution for seismic response of vertical shaft with primary and secondary linings under SH wave excitation. *Comput. Geotech.* 164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2023.105813>.
- Zhang, J., Bilotta, E., Madabhushi, G.S.P., Yuan, Y., 2023b. Numerical modelling of a tunnel adjacent to a surface structure in liquefiable ground. *Geotechnique*. Ahead of print. doi: 10.1680/jgeot.22.00418.
- Zhang, J., Bilotta, E., Sun, Q., Yuan, Y., 2024a. Numerical simulation and parametric analysis on a shallow tunnel in liquefiable ground subject to multiple shakings. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.* 183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2024.108802>.
- Zhang, J., Sun, M., Fan, Z., Yuan, Y., Sun, Q., 2024b. Shaking table test on shaft-tunnel junction in liquefiable sand site. *Tunn. Undergr. Sp. Tech.* 154, 106097. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2024.106097>.
- Zhang, X., Qin, H., Xu, Y., Qu, H., Chen, C., 2024c. Performance of an operational shield tunnel due to construction of a large cross-sectional straight-walled arch tunnel above-crossing. *Alex. Eng. J.* 108 (863–877), 863–877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2024.09.079>.